

Band structure, magneto-Seebeck and magnetoresistance at the para-to ferri-magnetic transition in the Sr₂FeReO₆ double perovskite

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ABSTRACT

Ferrimagnetic double perovskites provide a rare family of oxides where topological states might be responsible for effects at room temperature. In that respect, the effect of spin orbit coupling on the Sr₂FeReO₆ electronic structure has been calculated. This allows to predict an induced orbital moment (+0.32 μ_B) on Re oriented in the opposite direction with respect to the spin component and substantial anomalous Hall and Nernst conductivities. Experimentally, the negative magnetoresistance and positive magnetothermopower of a Sr₂FeReO₆ polycrystalline sample measured for temperatures below T_C = 405 K demonstrate that a positive thermoelectric power factor enhancement of +20 % in 9 T is achieved in the ferrimagnetic state at 336 K. However, at that temperature, we estimate that the magnitude of the anomalous Hall conductivity does not exceed 0.1 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹, which is much smaller than the calculated value of 33 Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The calculations likewise predict an anomalous Nernst conductivity contribution much larger than the observed experimental one, being below the resolution of our measurement. Several hypotheses are proposed to explain the discrepancies between prediction and experiments.

1. Introduction

As theoretically predicted [1–3] and experimentally verified for Sr₂FeMoO₆ crystals which show an anomalous Hall conductivity (AHC) contribution attributed to enhanced Berry curvature [4], the A₂BB'O₆ rock salt ordered double perovskites (DP) are a class of magnetic topological compounds. Such results are made possible by the ordering of the B and B' cations over the B-site of the ABO₃ perovskite lattice: a 3d magnetic cation in high spin state due to the crystal field splitting of its orbitals in octahedral coordination and a 4d or 5d element with a strong spin orbit coupling (SOC) [3]. As shown by the calculated spin polarized partial density of states of Sr₂FeMoO₆ and Sr₂FeReO₆ [4,5], the 4d/5d t_{2g} orbitals have the highest contribution at the Fermi level which makes the minority spin-down channel conducting, the spin-up one being gapped. In addition, the lifting of the band degeneracy by the SOC in Sr₂FeMoO₆ is responsible for gapped nodal lines, hence large AHC has been predicted and measured [4]. Similar calculations taking into account the SOC were made for many other double perovskites [3] but not for the Sr₂FeReO₆ ferrimagnet whose magnetic ordering temperature is

above room temperature, T_C varying in the range 401–445 K [5–11]. Accordingly, Sr₂FeReO₆ is a good candidate to look for topological effects at room temperature.

Furthermore, the enhancement of the thermopower by applying a magnetic field in MnGe and FeGe₂ that are also topological magnetic compounds [12,13] demonstrates how interesting is this class of materials for thermoelectricity (TE). This effect is known as positive magneto-thermopower (MTEP, calculated as [S_{9T}-S₀]/S₀, where S is for the Seebeck coefficient). In MnGe, concomitant positive MTEP and negative magnetoresistance MR [MR=(ρ_{9T}-ρ₀)/ρ₀, where ρ is for the electrical resistivity] indicate that the strong energy dependence of the transport lifetime (τ) in the ordered magnetic state is responsible for the H-dependence increase of S [12]. Indeed, from the Mott formula [14],

$$S = -(\pi^2 k_B^2 T / 3e) [(\partial \ln(D(E)/\partial E))|_{E=EF} + (\partial \ln(\tau(E)/\partial E))|_{E=EF}], \quad (1)$$

it was concluded that the second term dominates the MTEP effect as a result of unconventional carrier scattering, rather than the density of states first term D(E). With such a combination of MTEP > 0 and MR < 0, the thermoelectric performance is enhanced as the TE power factor

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($PF=S^2/\rho$) increases with the magnetic field. Such MTEP >0 is rarely encountered in itinerant magnetic compounds – (weak) ferromagnets and antiferromagnets – as the spin scattering reduction under magnetic field makes generally decreasing the spin entropy term of the Seebeck coefficient [15]. This is supported by MTEP measurements in several transition metal oxides: MTEP <0 was reported in paramagnetic layered cobaltites – NaCoO₂ and misfit [16,17] – and in the itinerant ferromagnet SrRuO₃ [18]. This outlines the rather unique behavior of double perovskites, with MTEP >0 in Ba₂FeMoO₆ [19] and MTEP >0 together with MR <0 in Sr₂FeReO₆ [11]. Even if the power factor remains modest, this shows that this magnetic field induced enhancement of the power factor can be observed up to 300K in these oxides. Nonetheless, since this last result was obtained from S and ρ measurements performed in the ferrimagnetic state, it is interesting to investigate at higher temperature ($T > T_C$). Furthermore, the Sr₂FeReO₆ electronic structure with SOC was not reported in the long list of A₂BB'O₆ magnetic double perovskites published in Ref. [3]. This motivated us to determine the Sr₂FeReO₆ electronic structure, to predict the magnetic and normal transport properties, and also to calculate the temperature dependence of topological transport phenomena such as AHC and anomalous Nernst conductivity (ANC). These results are then compared to magnetic, electrical and thermal characterizations in the full temperature range, revealing that for $T > T_C$ the MTEP and MR are almost equal to 0 whereas MTEP >0 and MR <0 are obtained just below T_C . A clear link between the beneficial effects on the power factor and the magnetization is thus established. AHC and ANE experimental magnitudes are discussed in the framework of the DFT predictions.

2. Techniques

2.1. Calculations

The double perovskite Sr₂FeReO₆ crystallizes in the $I4/m$ space group as previously reported [10]. The electronic structure calculations were performed using the room temperature structural parameters [10] within all-electron full-potential Wien2k APW + lo code [20] applying a Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA) with the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE96) exchange-correlation functional [21] combined with an additional effective on-site Coulomb potential $U_{eff} = U - J = 4$ eV and 1.5 eV laid on the Fe-3d and Re-5d states, respectively [21], whose spin states are aligned antiferromagnetically. Spin-orbit coupling (SOC) was applied on Re-5d and Fe-3d within the second variational procedure acting on spin-polarized eigenstates inside the atomic spheres ($R_{MT} = 2.0$ and 1.9 a.u., respectively) with the magnetization axis (001). The integration was performed within the first Brillouin zone (BZ) using a tetrahedron method on a mesh of $7 \times 7 \times 7$ k-points. The cut-off criterion $R_{MT} K_{max} = 7.0$ for plane waves expansion corresponds to the smallest muffin-tin radius of oxygen atom $R_{MT} = 1.6$ a.u. In the next step, the valence states wave functions of O-2p, Fe-3d and Re-5d around the Fermi energy were transformed into localized Wannier functions (Wannier90 code [22]). To explore the anomalous Hall conductivity σ_{xy} (AHC) and the anomalous Nernst conductivity α_{xy} (ANC), a tight-binding Hamiltonian (Wannier Tools 2.7.0 [23]) was further constructed using the Wannier orbitals. The Brillouin zone was sampled by $500 \times 500 \times 500$ division for the calculation of the Berry curvature $\Omega(k)$. The selection of (001) magnetization axis imposes a non-vanishing z-component $\Omega^z(k) = \sum_n f_{nk} \Omega_n^z(k)$ (f_{nk} standing for Fermi-Dirac distribution referred to the n th band), which can be expressed by Kubo formalism [24],

$$\Omega_n^z(k) = - \sum_{w \neq n} \frac{2\hbar I \langle \psi_{nk} | v_x | \psi_{wk} \rangle \langle \psi_{wk} | v_y | \psi_{nk} \rangle}{(\epsilon_{nk} - \epsilon_{wk})^2}. \quad (2)$$

A zero-temperature limit of the AHC was used, which was basically indistinguishable from using the finite-temperature AHC in our calculations. This allows to formally introduce an auxiliary quantity – an

energy-dependent AHC,

$$\sigma_{xy}(\epsilon) = \frac{-e^2}{\hbar} \int_{BZ} \frac{dk}{(2\pi)^3} \sum_{\epsilon_{nk} < \epsilon} \Omega_n^z(k), \quad (3)$$

describing contributions to AHC by electrons with energies lower than ϵ . The effect of finite temperature was implemented as

$$\sigma_{xy}(T) = \int d\epsilon \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mu} \sigma_{xy}(\epsilon), \quad (4)$$

where $f = 1/[e^{(\epsilon-\mu)/k_B T} + 1]$ is the Fermi-Dirac distribution function, μ being the chemical potential. The intrinsic ANC was obtained by the following expression [25],

$$\alpha_{xy}(T) = \frac{-1}{e} \int d\epsilon \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mu} \sigma_{xy}(\epsilon) \frac{\epsilon - \mu}{T} \quad (5)$$

2.2. Experimental

By considering the MTEP >0 of Sr₂FeReO₆, a polycrystalline sample was synthesized according to the protocol described in Refs. [10,11] and the refined unit cell parameters obtained from x-ray diffraction pattern are those expected for this composition. The structure was refined in the $I4/m$ space group with lattice parameters $a = 5.5621(1)\text{\AA}$ and $c = 7.8987(1)\text{\AA}$ [10]. Magnetization (M) as a function of temperature (up to 600 K) or magnetic field was collected in a 14T physical properties measurements system (PPMS from Quantum Design) with high temperature VSM option to cross the ferri-to paramagnetic transition. Electrical resistivity and thermopower (Seebeck coefficient) were collected in a 9T PPMS. Temperatures up to 580K were accessed under high vacuum using miniature heaters and a thermally isolated sample mount. Sample temperatures and voltages were sensed using R-type fine-wire thermocouples attached directly to the sample. The thermal gradient $\nabla_x T$ or current I_x was applied in the x-direction, the positive contact was placed at (0,w) and the negative contact at (l,0) where w was the sample width and l the distance between contacts along x . The magnetic field B_z was applied perpendicularly. In this configuration the voltage measured is a combination of both longitudinal and transverse effects. The resistivity and Seebeck effect are normally symmetric with respect to B_z , while the ordinary Hall and Nernst effects are antisymmetric. The anomalous Hall and Nernst effects will be distinguishable from the ordinary effects if a hysteresis loop opens. Thermal measurements were taken by stabilizing the temperature (and/or magnetic field) and then applying several thermal gradients by changing the power on the heaters at each end of the sample while maintaining the same average sample temperature. The thermoelectric response was confirmed to be linear in the applied thermal gradient at all points. DC current sweeps were used to collect the electrical response at each temperature/field. The apparatus and measurement protocol are functionally equivalent to the ZEM3 apparatus, although here the sample is in high vacuum for thermal isolation. The T -dependent data were merged with the low temperature ones collected with the same set-ups as in Ref. [11] recorded in cooling mode below 300 K.

3. Results

3.1. Calculations

The band structure of Sr₂FeReO₆ around the Fermi energy (E_F selected at 0 eV) and calculated with SOC is shown in Fig. 1. The valence band (VB) is predominantly constituted of valence oxygen O-2p orbitals ranging from -8 to -2 eV strongly hybridized with the Fe-3d spin-up states (both t_{2g} and e_g) at the bottom of VB and Re-5d spin down of t_{2g} symmetry pinned to E_F and being occupied by two electrons. This confirms, along with the absence of any occupied Fe-3d spin-down states,

Fig. 1. (a) Band structure calculated including SOC by Wien2k APW + lo basis (black) and after wannierization and transformation into tight binding Hamiltonian for an energy window $-9 - +5$ eV (orange), (b) density of states (DOS) with SOC for spin-up (blue) and spin-down (red, negative) channel. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

the valences Fe^{3+} and Re^{5+} [10], although the ferrimagnetically ordered spin magnetic moments $+3.96 \mu_B$ and $-0.96 \mu_B$ obtained by integrating the spin density over the respective muffin-tin spheres would rather suggest Fe^{2+} and Re^{6+} . This supports the antiferromagnetic coupling between the magnetic moments of the Fe and Re cations, similarly to the $+3.90 \mu_B$ and $-0.92 \mu_B$ values calculated for the Ba isostructural compound, $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ [3]. However, there is an additional spin density in the interstitial region ($-0.21 \mu_B$) as well as on the oxygen atoms ($+0.23 \mu_B$) indicating a notable $M-d - O-2p$ hybridization.

Without SOC the material would be a typical half-metal as already predicted [5] with the same band gap value of 2.4 eV in the spin-up channel separating $O-2p$ VB and empty $\text{Re}-t_{2g}$, while the spin-down structure is gapless with empty $\text{Fe}-3d$ bands smoothly merging the

partially filled $\text{Re}-t_{2g}$. This is confirming the first theoretical study of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ pointing towards the half-metallicity of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ with an expected 100 % spin polarization [5]. As shown in Fig. 1, switching on SOC brings about a mixing of both spin states in particular on $\text{Re}-5d$ and a population of some mid gap spin-up states. Although very small, the spin-up DOS for SOC calculation never reaches zero inside the original gap from -1.5 to 0.6 eV. Consequently, due to SOC, $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ is not a true half-metal any more contrasting with the first study [5]. While the orbital moment on Fe is negligible ($0.02 \mu_B$), the induced orbital moment $+0.32 \mu_B$ on Re oriented in the opposite direction with respect to the spin component is quite significant. This results in an increase of the total magnetic moment from 3.02 to $3.34 \mu_B$ per formula unit, as the orbital component on Re is parallel to the prevailing spin moment on Fe atom.

Fig. 2. Fermi surface formed by two $\text{Re}-t_{2g}$ bands (denoted by different colors) constructed from band structure calculated including spin-orbit (a) and without spin-orbit coupling (b). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Moreover, as clearly seen from the comparison shown in Fig. 2, SOC has a substantial effect on the Fermi surface shape and size and, at the same time, it represents an indispensable ingredient for topological transport phenomena such as AHC and ANC, whose calculated temperature dependences are displayed in Fig. 3a and b, respectively. The band degeneracy lifting leading to Berry curvature due to SOC is clearly visible on two parallel Re- t_{2g} bands crossing E_F along Z- Γ direction (Fig. 1a). The AHC absolute value shows a minimum near room temperature (Fig. 3), $|\sigma_{xy}| = 33 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, a value very similar to that calculated for $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ [3]. Indeed, the shapes of $\sigma_{xy}(E)$ would be very similar for the three compounds $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$, $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ [4] and $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ [3], though $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ has one less valence electron than the others. By removing one electron from $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$, E_F lowers by -0.464 eV in the insert of Fig. 3a where the slope is smoother than around $E_F = 0 \text{ eV}$. Therefore, one expects $\sigma_{xy}(E)$ of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ to be more sensitive to a small E shift than in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$. Quantitatively, for E_F reduced by -0.464 eV which would correspond to a pseudo $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$, one obtains $\sigma_{xy} = -43 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (from the data in Fig. 3a) which is very close to the intrinsic value derived from experimental data $\sigma_{xy} \approx -46.75 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ crystals [4]. For ANC, the α_{xy} value in the T_C region (405 K), $\alpha_{xy} = 0.4 \text{ A.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3b), is ten times higher than reported for $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ [3]. However, since at low temperature, $\alpha_{xy}(T)$ is approximately proportional to $d[\sigma_{xy}(E)]/dE$ (Eq. 10 in Ref 25), if a small energy shift induces a change of the $(d[\sigma_{xy}(E)]/dE)$ slope, then $\alpha_{xy}(T)$ also changes a lot.

Furthermore, the Ba^{2+} cations being larger than Sr^{2+} , the unit cell volume of $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ is bigger than its Sr analogue. Therefore, due to the corresponding narrower electronic bandwidth of $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeReO}_6$, the shape of $\sigma_{xy}(E)$ is compressed (shrunk). Accordingly, $\sigma_{xy}(E = 0)$ values will be similar for both double perovskites, but $\alpha_{xy}(T) \propto d[\sigma_{xy}(E)]/dE$ will be different with a higher sensitivity to a E_F shift for $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ than

Fig. 3. (a) Anomalous Hall conductivity as a function of temperature and energy around the Fermi level (inset), (b) anomalous Nernst conductivity, both calculated by Wannier tools [23].

$\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$.

3.2. Normal transport and magnetism

The $S(T)$ curve without applied magnetic field reveals $S > 0$ values with different dS/dT regimes: starting from 5 K, as T increases, S first increases up to 300 K (inset of Fig. 4, bottom panel) to reach a plateau with $S \approx 12 \mu\text{V/K}$ up to 400 K, and then S decreases (Fig. 4, bottom panel). Over the same temperature range, ρ shows a monotonous evolution, with ρ decreasing as T increases (Fig. 4, top panel). However, the comparison with the similar $S(T)$ and $\rho(T)$ measurements in 9 T (Fig. 4) shows a divergence starting below $\approx 400 \text{ K}$, with higher S and lower ρ values at 9 T than at 0 T, indicating MTEP > 0 and MR < 0 . This 0 T and 9 T curves divergence starting below about 400 K can be compared to the para-to ferrimagnetic transition observed in the same temperature region ($T_C = 405 \text{ K}$ taken at the inflection point of the magnetic transition) on the $M(T)$ curve collected in 0.1 T (Fig. 5). Additional isothermal $M(H)$ loops (Fig. 6) confirm the ferrimagnetic behavior with, at 300 K, $M_{5T} = 2.3 \mu_B/\text{f.u.}$ This value is smaller than the calculated one taking into account the SOC, $3.34 \mu_B/\text{f.u.}$, the latter being closer to the theoretical $3 \mu_B$, obtained by considering the antiferromagnetic coupling between the d^5 high spin electronic configuration of Fe^{3+} giving $5 \mu_B$ and the $2 \mu_B$ coming from the $5d^2$ configuration of Re^{5+} . This smaller measured value, already reported in previous studies [5,9,10], supports the existence of a certain degree of cation inter-mixing on the B and B' sites. As temperature increases, though at 460 K the $M(H)$ loop still exhibits some non-linearity, a clear linear behavior corresponding to

Fig. 4. (Top) T -dependent electrical resistivity $\rho(T)$ and (bottom) Seebeck coefficient $S(T)$ collected in 0 T and 9 T. In the insets, the data measured from 5K to 580K show clearly the occurrence of MR and MTEP below T_C . The two vertical dashed lines at 336 K and 460 K indicate the temperatures of the isothermal curves given in Fig. 7.

Fig. 5. T -dependence of the magnetic susceptibility (χ) collected upon warming from 5 K after a zero field cooling (zfc) and field cooling (fc) in 0.1 T.

Fig. 6. Isothermal H -dependence of the magnetization collected at different temperatures labelled in the graph.

paramagnetism is observed at 550 K (Fig. 6, inset). The comparison of the temperature dependence of M , S and ρ confirms that the measured MTEP > 0 and MR < 0 effects corresponds to the setting of ferrimagnetism.

In order to confirm these MTEP and MR effects, isothermal $S(H)$ and $\rho(H)$ measurements were collected at 336 K and 460 K (Fig. 7), i.e. below and above T_C . The $M(H)_{336K}$ curve (Fig. 6) shows a hysteresis loop characteristic of ferrimagnetism. At 336 K, the $S(H)$ (Fig. 7, bottom) and $\rho(H)$ (Fig. 7, top) curves are characterized by two main regimes, with $\propto H^2$ or $\propto H$ dependence below and above 2 T, a magnetic field value that also corresponds approximately to a change of $M(H)$ regime (Fig. 6). At the maximal magnetic field ($=9$ T), one obtains a negative MR of -4% and a positive MTEP of $+8\%$, whose combination leads to a 20% increase of the PF= S^2/ρ . The same types of measurement performed at 460 K do not show any magnetic field effect, confirming that the MTEP > 0 and MR < 0 are related to the ferrimagnetic ordered state. The $S(H)$ curves in Fig. 7 may contain a small ordinary Nernst contribution of the order of $0.1 \mu V K^{-1}$ in 9 T. We have not attempted to remove this since

Fig. 7. H -dependent ρ (top panel) and S (bottom panel) curves recorded at 336 K (red) and 460 K (blue). The inset in the top panel is an enlargement of the $\rho(H)_{336K}$. The data were recorded in the configuration where the voltage measured is a combination of both longitudinal and transverse effects. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

this magnitude is similar to the measurement reproducibility as shown by the spread of the points taken at the same magnetic fields but at different times as part of the hysteresis loop. This may reflect a drift in the measurement over time.

3.3. Anomalous transport

The small hysteresis in $M(H)$ curves at applied magnetic field < 0.2 T is also seen as an anomalous Hall contribution to the resistivity (inset of top panel of Fig. 7), although the data at 336 K are dominated by a large ordinary magnetoresistance which makes quantitative evaluation difficult. We estimate that the magnitude of the anomalous Hall conductivity does not exceed $0.1 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, which is much smaller than the calculated value of $33 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3a) for the same temperature. The experimental value of $0.1 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ is obtained at $E = 26.4$ meV, which corresponds to a thermal energy of $T = 306$ K. Therefore, in practice, Fermi-level shifts must be taken into account due to electron doping and temperature effects that push the Fermi level upward.

The calculations likewise predict an anomalous Nernst conductivity contribution of $\approx 0.4 \text{ A.m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3b). Given the other measured quantities this should result in a Nernst signal of $\approx 60 \mu V K^{-1}$, which would dominate the thermoelectric response and would be easily visible in our measurement. However, any experimentally determined ANC value is below the resolution of our measurement, which as we noted in the section above, is around $0.1 \mu V K^{-1}$. As mentioned in the previous calculations section, relatively small shifts of the Fermi level can cause

the calculated values of the anomalous transport coefficients to become much smaller (as seen in the inset to Fig. 3a), and may explain the discrepancy between the calculation and experimental data.

4. Conclusion

The theoretical part of the study shows that the spin polarized transport in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$, typical of a half-metal behavior, is modified by SOC switching in the calculation. First, it brings a significant induced orbital moment of $+0.32 \mu_B$ on Re oriented in the opposite direction with respect to the spin component. The values with or without SOC being larger than the experimental ones, it suggests that the fully polarized transport is hindered by some degree of structural defects, like Fe/Re anti-site defects, change of cation oxidation states, oxygen non stoichiometry, which would reduce the spin polarization. As expected from previous theoretical studies for other magnetic double perovskites [3], in $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ also, switching on the SOC in the calculations yields topological transport phenomena like AHC and ANC. The obtained calculated values of AHC for $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ (this study) and $\text{Ba}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ [3] are very similar but the ANC ones differ by one order of magnitude, the values for $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ being 10 times larger. This can be understood considering that $\alpha_{xy}(T)$ is even more sensitive than σ_{xy} to small shift in E_F .

Experimentally, S and ρ measurements below and above T_C demonstrate that $\text{MTEP} > 0$ and $\text{MR} < 0$ are related to ferrimagnetism, these quantities becoming null in the paramagnetic state. Thus, as compared to other topological magnetic materials like MnGe or FeGe₂ [12,13], the double perovskites offer the possibility to study MTEP and MR at room temperature. For the ANC and AHC transverse effects, to explain the experimental values smaller than those predicted, the spin polarization reduction deduced from the too small measured magnetic moment can be considered. If the spin polarization decreases, the two bands with different signs of the Berry's curvature become closer, then the (+) and (−) Berry's curvatures get compensated. Therefore, the degree of spin polarization affects the strength of both AHC and ANC. In contrast a good agreement between calculated and intrinsic AHC values extracted from the measurements was observed in the case of $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeMoO}_6$ crystals [4], despite the measured magnetization for the latter was also found smaller than the theoretical one. This suggests that the polycrystalline form of the studied $\text{Sr}_2\text{FeReO}_6$ sample might weaken the anomalous effects. This was the case in the $\text{Co}_3\text{Sn}_2\text{S}_2$ Weyl semi-metal for which the anomalous Nernst effect maximum value was reduced by 2 as compared to that of crystals [26]. In that respect, this study calls for more experimental work on double perovskites to reveal the existence of the predicted very large topological effects at room temperature.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ramzy Daou: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **David Sedmidubský:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Kyohoon Ahn:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Sylvie Hébert:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Raul E. Carbonio:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Christine Martin:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Antoine Maignan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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